

Expectation from Instagram Data Exports

Dear participant,

This survey seeks to understand what insights you expect to gain when accessing your personal data through GDPR data exports on Instagram. Under the GDPR, Article 15, you have the right to request and download a copy of your personal data from various platforms, which includes the information they collect about you.

This survey is being conducted jointly by academic researchers from XYZ. Your valuable opinion expressed in this survey may contribute to important research findings. So, we request you to read the instructions carefully and answer all the questions judiciously.

Results from the survey may be published in a research forum. The insights will be published in aggregate forms (such as averages and/or totals). We will neither publish nor share any information which can disclose any of your confidential information. All information will be protected to the greatest extent allowed by law, and data will be kept secured during and after the survey.

🚫⚠️ Please do not use ChatGPT or any other large language models (LLMs) to generate your responses. We are specifically seeking your personal thoughts. If we determine that your responses are AI-generated, you may not be eligible for compensation. ⚠️🚫

Selecting the "Agree" button indicates the following:

1. You have read the above information.
2. You voluntarily agree to participate in the "Expectation from Instagram Data Exports" survey.

* Indicates required question

1. I consent; begin the survey. *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

2. Please enter your Prolific ID here *

Background on GDPR Chapter 3: Rights of the Data Subjects

Under the GDPR Chapter 3 (Article 15), users have the right to request and download a copy of their personal data from various platforms, which includes the information they collect about you.

Let's take Instagram for an example. If you have been using Instagram short form video platform, you can go and request your data on the Instagram App and get a snippet of your data.

For the process of how to request your data and how a standard Instagram data looks like please refer to the information at this given url: [here](#)

3. Before taking this survey, were you aware of having such rights to access your personal data gathered by different online platforms? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No

4. If yes, how did you know about these rights? *

Insights you expect from the Instagram Data - Browsing history

From here, we show different types of personal data like your browsing history, likes, etc. that you could see in your data exports upon request. We want to know what questions or insights about your activities would you be curious to know or understand from your data.

Instagram shares your recent **browsing history** with you in the following format (each entry contains only the fields shown below), what kind of insights would you be curious to know or understand from this data?

Author : Virat.kohli
Time : Aug 29, 2024, 9:18 AM

5. Question - 1 *

6. Question - 2

7. Question - 3

Insights you expect from the Instagram Data - Search history

Instagram shares your recent **search history** with you in the following format (each entry contains only the fields shown below), what kind of insights would you be curious to know or understand from this data?

Search history

Search : Chicken sandwich

Time : Aug 29, 2024, 9:18 AM

8. Question - 1 *

9. Question - 2

10. Question - 3

Insights you expect from the Instagram Data - Comments

Instagram shares your **comments** with you in the following format (each entry contains only the fields shown below), what kind of insights would you be curious to know or understand from this data?

Comments

Comment : Loving this vibe! 🔥🔥

Media Owner : Virat.kohli

Time : Aug 29, 2024, 9:18 AM

11. Question - 1 *

12. Question - 2

13. Question - 3

Insights you expect from the Instagram Data - Save History

Instagram shares your **saved posts** with you in the following format (each entry contains only the fields shown below), what kind of insights would you be curious to know or understand from this data?

Save History

Author : Virat.kohli

Saved : <https://www.instagram.com/p/DJiwQm0RbiM/>

Saved on : Aug 29, 2024, 9:18 AM

14. Question - 1 *

15. Question - 2

16. Question - 3

Insights you expect from the Instagram Data - Connections

Instagram shares your **connections(followers/following)** with you in the following format (each entry contains only the fields shown below), what kind of insights would you be curious to know or understand from this data?

Connections

Author : [Virat.Kohli](#)
Time : Aug 29, 2024, 9:18 AM

17. Question - 1 *

18. Question - 2

19. Question - 3

Insights you expect from the Instagram Data - Like history

Instagram shares your **Like History** with you in the following format (each entry contains only the fields shown below), what kind of insights would you be curious to know or understand from this data?

Like history

Author : Virat_kohli
Liked: <https://www.instagram.com/p/DJiwQm0RbiM/>
Time : Aug 29, 2024, 9:18 AM

20. Question - 1 *

21. Question - 2

22. Question - 3

Insights you expect from the Instagram Data - Off platform activities

Instagram shares your **Off Platform Activity** with you in the following format (each entry contains only the fields shown below, there will be **multiple entries for each app/website** you visit), what kind of insights would you be curious to know or understand from this data?

Off platform activities

<p>Activity from lifestores.com</p> <hr/> <p>ID : 208055972868053</p> <p>Event : VIEW_CONTENT</p> <p>Time : Aug 29, 2024, 9:18 AM</p>
--

23. Question - 1 *

24. Question - 2

25. Question - 3

Insights you expect from the Instagram Data - Login history

Instagram shares your **login history** with you in the following format (each entry contains only the fields shown below), what kind of insights would you be curious to know or understand from this data?

Login history

```
Date : Oct 14, 2024 1:51AM CET
Cookie name : *****1223
IP : 00.00.00.00
Language Code : en

User Agent : Mozilla/5.0 (Windows NT 10.0;
Win64; x64) AppleWebKit/537.36 (KHTML, like
Gecko) Chrome/117.0.0.0 Safari/537.36
```

26. Question - 1 *

27. Question - 2

28. Question - 3

Insights you expect from the Instagram Data - Devices

Instagram shares your **devices you used** with you in the following format (each entry contains only the fields shown below), what kind of insights would you be curious to know or understand from this data?

Devices

Last Login : Oct 14, 2024 1:51 AM CET

User Agent : Mozilla/5.0 (Windows NT 10.0; Win64; x64) AppleWebKit/537.36 (KHTML, like Gecko) Chrome/117.0.0.0 Safari/537.36

29. Question - 1 *

30. Question - 2

31. Question - 3

Summary & Self-Assessment

In this section, please reflect on how well you think you can understand and interpret your data on your own.

32. Would you like to gain any other insights from your Instagram data?

Please write each insight / question with a line break. As shown below:

What websites did I visit the most?

When did I last visit a site?

33. Have you ever requested your personal data from instagram? *

Mark only one oval.

Yes

No *Skip to question 37*

Summary & Self-Assessment (Continuation)

In this section, please reflect on how well you think you can understand and interpret your data on your own.

34. What was the reason for requesting data from instagram? *

35. Roughly, what percentage of questions that you mentioned during the survey were you able to infer from your data? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

0% (100% (All))

36. How confident are you that you can find the answers to your questions from the data on your own? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5

Not Very confident

About you

In this section, you will be asked a series of questions about yourself. None of these sensitive details will be shared in a way which will jeopardize your privacy.

37. You describe yourself as *

Mark only one oval.

- Male
- Female
- Prefer not to say
- Other: _____

38. Age (in years) *

Mark only one oval.

18-25

25-30

30-40

40+

39. Which of the platforms do you use? *

Check all that apply.

Facebook

Instagram

Tiktok

Youtube

LinkedIn

Snapchat

Twitter

40. Occupation *

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Google.

Google Forms